

SERUM ELECTROLYTE CONCENTRATION OF LEAD ACETATE COMPROMISED RATS TREATED WITH AQUEOUS LEAF EXTRACT OF *Moringa oleifera* AND *Cymbopogon citratus*

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Abstract

This study was conducted to determine the effect of the co-administration of aqueous leaf extracts of *Moringa oleifera* and *Cymbopogon citratus* on serum electrolyte levels of Lead acetate exposed female Wistar rats. Thirty adult female Wistar rats were divided into six groups of five per group were used for this study. Group 1 served as normal control and received only water and normal feed *ad libitum*. Lead acetate was administered to groups 2,3,4,5 and 6 daily for 15 days at 150 mg/kg body weight, thereafter, the same dose was administered every other day till the end of the experiment. Groups 3, 4, 5 and 6 were administered with aqueous extracts of *M. oleifera* and *C. citratus* at 1500 mg/kg b.w. at the ratio of 50:50 and combined extract of *M. oleifera* and *C. citratus* at a dose of 3000 mg/kg b.w at the ratio of 50:50 respectively, daily for 56 days. The serum electrolyte levels were assayed at the end of the experiment. A significant increase ($P < 0.05$) in the mean serum sodium and chloride levels was observed in group 6 when compared to the control. The sodium levels in groups 2, 3, 4 and 5 were non-significant ($P > 0.05$) while chloride levels in groups 2 and 3 significantly increased ($P < 0.05$) when compared to group 1. There was no significant difference in Calcium levels in groups 2, 3, 4 and 6 when compared to group 1. Bicarbonate levels revealed a non-significant change ($P > 0.05$) in groups 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6 when compared to control. Conclusively, *Moringa oleifera* and *Cymbopogon citratus* tend to alter serum electrolytes levels at the doses administered.